

Research Article

Surface Water and Groundwater Recharge Modeling in Sunsari District using Integrated SWAT-MODFLOW Model

Jangbahadur Prasad Yadav¹, Jawed Alam², Bhesh Raj Thapa³, Rocky Talchabhadel⁴, AK Mishra⁵

¹ Scholar, Purwanchal Engineering Campus (IOE), Tribhuvan University, Nepal and Assistant Professor, Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal, Uurlabari-3, Morang, Nepal.

² Purwanchal Engineering Campus (IOE), Tribhuvan University, Nepal

³ Universal Engineering and Science College, Lalitpur, Nepal.

⁴ Texas A & M AgriLife Research, Texas A & M University, El Paso, TX, USA.

⁵ Associate Professor, Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal, Uurlabari-3, Morang, Nepal.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24321/2393.8307.202202>

I N F O

Corresponding Author:

Anjay Kumar Mishra, Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal, Uurlabari 3, Morang, Nepal.

E-mail Id:

anjaymishra2000@gmail.com

Orcid Id:

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2803-4918>

How to cite this article:

Yadav JP, Alam J, Thapa BR et al. Surface Water and Groundwater Recharge Modeling in Sunsari District using Integrated SWAT-MODFLOW Model. *J Adv Res Civil Envi Engr* 2022; 9(1&2): 12-22.

Date of Submission: 2022-04-10

Date of Acceptance: 2022-05-10

A B S T R A C T

This study employs an integrated groundwater-surface water (GW-SW) model, using SWAT-MODFLOW, to assess groundwater recharge and withdrawals at a regional scale in eastern Nepal. The model components were calibrated and validated using monthly river flow and hydraulic head data for the 1979-2017 period. Our results demonstrate that the average annual groundwater discharge is 2.43 m³/s. Seasonally, the average groundwater discharge is 2.73 m³/s during Summer and is 2.13 m³/s during winter. We observe that the maximum (6.9 m³/s) and minimum (0.036 m³/s) rates occurred in September-October and March-April, respectively. We also find that the average runoff fraction (i.e., runoff/ precipitation) varied from 0.34 to 0.72, and the ET component varied from 0.24 to 0.547 of the total precipitation within the SWAT model. The yearly fluctuation in TWS varied from $\pm 9.9\%$ to $\pm 58\%$ of the total precipitation. The Aquifer thickness varies from 16m to 57 m, and the specific yield in the Sunsari district varied from 0.12 lps to 890 lps. In the southern part, we see the water level declines from 2-4 m from July to August, where the bottom water slowly declines in September. The recharge of 1380 l/sec is observed in the Sapta Koshi area in the Bhabar zone. There is substantial underflow from hills simultaneously, resulting in the total recharge in the Sunsari district of 1.98 MCM/yr. At the same time, the total discharge, including surface, sub-surface, and spring water discharge, is nearly 29.2 MCM/yr. This study shows that the Sunsari district's water resources have many groundwater and surface water, properly managed for future use.

Keywords: Digital Elevation Model, Swat Model, Modflow Model, Integrated Swat-Modflow Model, Sapta-Koshi River Basin

Introduction

Effective water assets the board has become more testing because of expanding struggle among various water use areas like homegrown, modern, and farming (Loucks PD, van Beek 1981; Mishra AK 2018; Mishra AK & Karna AK 2019). A few investigations break down different hydrological parts connected with surface water, yet groundwater parts were not considered quite well. Groundwater is viewed as a basic wellspring of new water (Hamilton 2005). According to Mishra AK (2019), the water needs to be institutionalized immediately for effective operation. Sound getting it and measurement of groundwater re-energize are significant for overseeing groundwater assets for the conjunctive utilization of surface water and groundwater (Bambara et al. 2020). The GW-SW collaboration inside a watershed is a vital variable since they are profoundly interconnected (Dwarakish and Ganasri 2015). The investigation of timing and spatial area of groundwater release to streams is expected because of three significant reasons: i) upgrade conjunctive utilization of groundwater and surface water ((Putthividhya and Laonamsai 2017), ii) assess the responsiveness of stream streams and amphibian species to evolving environment (Putthividhya and Laonamsai 2017), groundwater extraction (Gupta, Mukherjee, and Bhattacharya 2018), or land-use modifications, and iii) evaluate the capability of regions with higher base-stream to give asylum to temperature-delicate species under environmental change (ZOMORODI 1991).

Numerous methods have been utilized to appraise GW-SW collaboration at different spatial and fleeting scales. Explicit field strategies remember playing out a water balance for stream comes to (de Silva and Rushton 2007). These examinations are performed at little spatial scales (Hughes 2004) and over a brief period (Kim, Chung, and Won 2004), albeit a few investigations (Zhou and Li 2011) have been applied to local scales. For evaluating at bigger spatial-fleeting scales, mathematical displaying approaches have been utilized, for instance, utilizing MODFLOW-UZF (de Silva and Rushton 2007) to a 500 km² district of the Lower Arkansas River Valley in southeastern Colorado (Varni et al. 2013) to examine the change in groundwater return stream designs under differing water system the board techniques, and applying GSFLOW (Kim et al. 2008) to a 80 km² granitic catchment in Spain, and utilizing a coupled GSFLOW-SWMM model to research communications under different water-use situations in the farming concentrated Zhengyi Basin, China (Dwarakish and Ganasri 2015). Coordinated hydrological models like PARFLOW (Hashemi, Berndtsson, and Persson 2015) have additionally been applied at little spatial scales, for example, a 5-km reach of the Cosumnes River in California (Walraevens et al. 2009). The review district is the Sprague River Watershed in the Upper Klamath Basin, Oregon, USA, wherein streamflow

is emphatically reliant upon groundwater release along specific spans (Brunner et al. 2010). Streamflow is firmly dependent on groundwater release (Brunner et al. 2010).

We survey a new groundwater model that couples the most recent variants of the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT), recreating water, supplement, and residue transport at the watershed scale. Soil Conservation Services and Curve Number (SCS-CN) strategy is primogeniture and the easiest technique for precipitation spillover displaying. Land cover data is utilized in hydrological displaying to gauge the worth of surface unpleasantness or erosion as it influences the speed of the overland progression of water (Ara and Zakwan 2018). The SCS Curve Number strategy is broadly utilized in light of its adaptability and straightforwardness (Askar 2014). Contingent upon the extent of the exploration studies, models can be applied to locales of fundamentally changing size and intricacy. To make exact figures, mathematical models that evaluate water assets ought to be all encompassing, zeroing in on groundwater and surface water together as opposed to treating them exclusively. The incorporated model enjoys a few upper hands over existing renditions ((Loukika et al. 2020), (Brunner et al. 2010), (Dong, Li, and Xu 2012), (Liu et al. 2019), (Chunn et al. 2019, for example, geologically found Hydrologic Response Units (HRUs); a productive HRU-framework cell planning plan; the capacity to utilize SWAT and MODFLOW models of various spatial degree; and utilization of the Newton definition of MODFLOW-2005 ((Bailey et al. 2016) for the ideal arrangement of situations including pheonmena of drying and rewetting nonlinearities of the unconfined groundwater-stream condition.

We utilized the openly accessible coupled model SWAT-MODFLOW model, which has been tried in numerous watersheds. This model works with assessing surface release, sub-surface release, groundwater stream, re-energize, the impacts of the well release of the review region, and surface water system on groundwater in a watershed (Bailey et al. 2016). Many examinations (Aliyari et al. 2019; Bailey et al. 2016, 2017; Beven 2012; Brunner et al. 2010; Chunn et al. 2019; Cooley 2011; Dong et al. 2012; Dowlatabadi and Ali Zomorodian 2016; Ehtiat et al. 2016; EshTawi, Evers, and Tischbein 2016; Gao et al. 2019; Hashemi et al. 2015; Karimi, Motagh, and Entezam 2019; Kim et al. 2008, 2004; Liu et al. 2019; Loukika et al. 2020; Melaku and Wang 2019; Moghaddam et al. 2019; Mosase et al. 2019; Park et al. 2019a, 2019b; Putthividhya and Laonamsai 2017; Ricka et al. 2018; Rossetto et al. 2018; Sherring, Abdul Rahman, and Arpan 2016; Taie Semiromi and Koch 2019; Walraevens et al. 2009; Wei and Bailey 2019; Xu et al. 2012; Xu and Van Tonder 2001; Zhou and Li 2011, 2011) have been directed for evaluation of the exactness of coupled SWAT-MODFLOW model in various districts of the world.

In this review, we tried to investigate this model's proficiency and apply it in eastern Nepal. We pick the Sunsari regions in the Sapta Koshi stream bowl as the review region due to the accessibility of an organization of hydro-meteorological stations. This bowl addresses the huge measured watersheds of the eastern district of Nepal. This study plans to evaluate the effectiveness of coupled SWAT-MODFLOW model as for record information in the review region.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was conducted at the Sapta Koshi river basin in Nepal located at the latitudes between 26°51' and 29°79' N and longitudes between 85°24' and 88°57' E, which originated from the mountains and drained to Ganges river in India by passing through low lands of Terai. Figures 1 a-b-c show the location map of the study area in Nepal. Figure 1 (d) shows elevation ranges from about 38 m above mean sea level (amsl) to 8254 m amsl. Figure 1 (e) shows the spatial distribution of land used (MAP) across the study area, and lastly, Figure 1 (f) shows the Soil classification within the study area. The average precipitation in the study area is 1600 mm in the terai area and 3800 mm in hills, and the average temperature varies from 19°C to 32°C. The average humidity is 80%, according to data from 1979 to 2015 provided by the Department of Hydrology and Meteorology (DHM), Nepal. The well depth varies from 13.7 m to 30.2 m and 55 m to 120 m for shallow well and deep well, respectively.

Figure 1.a) Location of the study area, b) Koshi basin for Swat Simulation and c) the study area of Coupled Swat-Modflow model d) Topographical map e) land use map f) Soil types map

SWAT Model for Koshi Basin

ARC-SWAT 2012 was used to build the SWAT model of the study area. This model was used in predicting and assessing surface water flow in the study area. A digital elevation model (DEM) was first imported in ARC-SWAT to delineate the watershed, where we divide the basin into 37 sub-basins, as shown in Figures 2 (a). The model calculates the direction and accumulation of surface water flow based on low points. The soil used and land used data of the study

area were imported via components-based GIS layer. The Hydrological Response Unit (HRU) represents the smallest hydrological unit with a unique combination of local soil, land used, slope characteristics.

Historical weather data, including Precipitation, Temperature, Relative Humidity, Wind speed, and Solar radiation, were collected from the Department of Hydrology and Meteorology of Nepal for 1979-2017. The calibrated SWAT result was clipped for the Sunsari district. Sunsari district was again sub-division of 64 Sub-basin as shown in Figures 2 (b).

Figure 2.a) koshi Watershed With hydrological Station and sub-basin and 2 (b) Sunsari Watershed With sub-basin

Development of SCS Curve method for Sunsari District

The SCS-CN (1985) method was developed in 1954 by USDA SCS (SRINIVAS, RAO, and GURUNADHA RAO 1999). This method is used to calculate Surface runoff using the Curve number, which is a combination of land used in the study area and the soil class, and the elevation and composition of soil composition. This study estimates the curve number for each sub-basin by combining DEM, land used, and hydrological classification of soil using ARC-SWAT 2012. The precipitation variation in Sunsari was 1600 mm/yr to 4500 mm/yr, as shown in Figures 3 (a), while the SCS curve number of the study area was varied from 60 to 100 (refer to Figures 3 (b)). The SCS method used on the basic formula as.

Where Q is a surface runoff in mm, P is the rainfall depth in mm, Ia is the initial abstraction in mm and S is the potential maximum retention.

SWAT-MODFLOW Model Development

SWAT-MODFLOW modeling is coded into a single FORTRAN code that is compiled and run as a single executable. The basic process of linking the SWAT output HRU calculated deep percolation to pass and MODFLOW model as recharge to the grid cells of MODFLOW. SWAT calculates the volume of surface flow and lateral flow to streams through the watershed stream network. In contrast, MODFLOW calculates groundwater discharge volume to streams,

where the River package of MODFLOW is used for a GW-SW interaction in simulation. This package uses Darcy's law to calculate the volumetric flow of water through the cross-sectional flow area between the aquifer and the stream channel. The basic input of the integrated model is Hydraulic conductivity, aquifer thickness, specific yield, and DEM of the study area, which is essential with well observation and HRU deep percolation of SWAT outputs. The integrated SWAT-MODFLOW model SWAT HRUs must be converted disaggregated, after which named as DHRUs. The convert HRU into polygons which allows connection between SWAT and MODFLOW. DHRUs pass location and SW flow data to MODFLOW grid cells on daily time steps, which is returned to SWAT to calculate the hydraulic head and GW-SW interaction flow rates.

Figure 3.(a) and 3 (b) shows Annual Precipitation (mm) and CN number calculation in Sunsari District

Result and Discussion

SWAT Model Calibration Parameters

Calibration guidelines are described within the documentation for the SWAT-CUP software and were implemented in this study. Within the SWAT software, the model runs successfully for the simulated duration of 38 years. For the optimal run, a warm-up period of three years was used, bringing the first data year to 1984. The model was then calibrated using observed monthly streamflow data at two hydrometric stations within the study area (Outlet Gauge and Tributary Gauge). We used the Sequential Uncertainty Fitting program (SUF12) for this study. We performed sensitivity analyses to work out which parameters most affect the streamflow simulation. The calibration procedure starts by providing a large range that we defined. However, this first range is physically meaningful and is predicated on an input file obtained from different sources. For example, soil-related parameters like soil hydraulic conductivity (K) and soil Available Water Capacity (AWC) are attributed to the soil map. They are initially obtained by taking soil samples and analyzing soil profiles in separate studies by the data providers. Default parameters provide a base for the modeler to make decisions about the initial parameter range. The parameter range narrows down through an iterative procedure until the simplest performing parameter range is obtained. The sensitive parameters of at Chatra station are listed below in Table 1.

Table 1. Calibrated Sensitive Parameters

Parameters	Description	Range		Calibration results		
		Lower	Upper	Fitted value	Method	Sensitivity
CN ₂ .mgt	Initial SCS CNII value	-25	30	1.15	Multiply	Most sensitive
Sol Awc.sol	Available water capacity (mmH ₂ O/mm soil)	-25	35	0.95	Multiply	Most sensitive
Canmx.hru	Maximum Canopy Storage, (mm H ₂ O)	0	10	3.5	Replace	Most sensitive
Gw Delay.gw	Groundwater Delay (days)	0	500	11	Replace	Most sensitive
Ch K2.rte	Hydraulic conductivity in main channel, mm/h	0	150	55	Replace	Most sensitive
CH N.rte	Manning's Roughness in main canal	0	1	0.055	Replace	Most sensitive
SURLAG.bsn	surface runoff lag time (day)	1	24	1.5	Replace	Most sensitive
SFTMP.bsn	Snowfall temperature, °C	-5	5	1.9	Replace	Moderate sensitive
SMTMP.bsn	Snowmelt base temperature, °C	-5	5	3.3	Replace	Moderate sensitive
SMFMX.bsn	Melt factor for snow on June 21 (mm H ₂ O/°C/day)	0	10	6	Replace	Moderate sensitive
SMFMN.bsn	Melt factor for snow on December 21 (mm H ₂ O/°C/day)	0	10	2.4	Replace	Moderate sensitive
TIMP.bsn	Snowpack temperature lag factor	0	1	0.61	Replace	Moderate sensitive

The hydrograph of daily calibrated value and observed value is shown in Figure 5, which shows the model is calibrated to the flow is very well. The hydrographs are also in good agreement with the rainfall pattern. The values of the Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency (ENS), Coefficient of determination (R^2), Percentage BIAS, and Percentage Error Volume (PEV) are used as objective functions to determine the predictive capability of the model.

Model Calibration Results and Simulated Results

This model was calibrated at Chatara Station from 1985 to 1994 with a warm-up period of 5 years and then validated from 1995 to 2014. The observed and Calibrated streamflows at the Chatara station are shown in Figure (4), Figure (5), and figure (6) on daily, monthly, and yearly scales, respectively. Similarly, observed and simulated streamflow at the Chatara station are presented in Figure (7).

Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6 shows Calibrated (solid orange) and observed (solid blue) daily, Monthly and Yearly stream discharge while Figure 7, Figure 8 and Figure 9 shows Simulated (solid orange) and observed (solid blue) daily, Monthly and Yearly stream discharge

Table 2.Values of objective functions for evaluating the performance of SWAT model for Chatara Station

Parameters	Calibration Periods (1984-1994)			Validation Periods (1995-2014)		
	Daily	Monthly	Yearly	Daily	Monthly	Yearly
R^2	0.68	0.84	0.96	0.65	0.80	0.92
NSE	0.65	0.78	0.92	0.63	0.74	0.90
PBIAS	0.042 %	0.018 %	0.015 %	0.052 %	0.021 %	0.018 %
PEV	0.0092 %	0.003 %	0.0021 %	0.0096 %	0.0032 %	0.003%

Table 3.Swat-model result summary

Periods	Parameters	Daily		Monthly		Yearly	
		Observed	Result	Observed	Result	Observed	Result
Calibration	Max. flow (m^3/sec)	9610	9604	6046	6038	1831	1822
	Min. flow (m^3/sec)	201	254	297	298	1383	1420
	Average Flow (m^3/sec)	1641	1640	1665	1656	1643	1639
Validation	Max. flow (m^3/sec)	9480	9807	6275	6258	2065	2052
	Min. flow (m^3/sec)	201	100	230	220	1155	1150
	Average Flow (m^3/sec)	1455	1453	1447	1440	29104	29009

Figure (8), and Figure (9) on daily, monthly, and yearly scales, respectively. The summary of the model's performance is shown in table 2 and table 3.

Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6 shows Calibrated (solid orange) and observed (solid blue) dail, Monthly and Yearly stream discharge while Figure 7, Figure 8 and Figure 9 shows Simulated (solid orange) and observed (solid blue) daily, Montly and Yearly stream discharge.

Surface Water Components of Koshi Basin

In the Koshi basin, the average precipitation value is about 1800 mm. The annual average precipitation in the terai area is less than 1400 mm. It is 1800 mm in the Hilly area and approximately 2500 mm in the mountain region (refer to figure 10). The surface discharge of the Koshi basin is almost 45 % of average precipitation. The surface runoff is less than 300 mm in the Mountain region and 301mm to 650 mm in the Hilly region, while it is more than 1000 mm in the Terai region (refer to Figure 11). Almost 38% of average rainfall is lost as evapotranspiration loss which is shown in Figure 12. This is also varying as in variation in precipitation and surface runoff. This loss is found less than 400 mm in the mountain region and 401mm to 500 mm in the hilly region. While it is seen substantial in the Terai region that was more than 1150 mm. this is due to the concentration of time, and most of the water body lies in the Terai region.

Figure 12. Spatial distribution of Evapotranspiration Loss in Koshi Basin (1985-2014)
Water balance Component in Sunsari District

The average precipitation of Sunsari district is observed 1868 mm with a range from 1100 mm to 2300 mm, as seen in Figure 13. Precipitation in most of the inner terai area ranges from 1300 mm to 1700 mm, and at the middle area and it is 1700 mm to 2000 mm while is more than 2000 mm near the Hilly area. The average surface discharge of the Sunsari district is 43 % of the average rainfall of the district.

Figure 10 and Figure 11. Spatial distribution of average Precipitation and Surface Runoff in Koshi Basin (1985-2014)

Figure 13. Water Components of Sunsari District (1985-2014)

The surface runoff is found less than 181 mm in the hilly area while it is 700 mm to 800 mm while it is more than 900 mm in the inner terai of Sunsari district. The lateral flow from the surface to the ground is found almost 8% of rainfall, varying from 20 mm to 250 mm in stream bank area while it varies 100 mm to 150 mm in most of the inner Terai rea while it is less than 50 mm in the hilly area. The evapotranspiration loss from the Sunsari district is found very low that is only 4% of the total rainfall. In comparison, water yield is found that 50 % of the total rainfall in the Sunsari district. The water components of Sunsari District are shown in Figure 13.

Figure 14. Comparison of Swat output SCS curve method and coupled SWAT-MODFLOW model each basin

Figure 15. SWAT model and Coupled SWAT-MODFLOW result at Dharan

Comparison of Surface Discharge Result using SWAT, SCS, and Coupled SWAT_MODFLOW model

SWAT-MODFLOW results are very much similar to the

observed hydrograph stream discharge of the Sunsari district. For the validation of the model, it is compared with values at Chatara station. The NS and R² computed are R²= 0.84, and NS = 0.98 on a daily scale, and R²= 0.87, and NS = 0.92 on a monthly scale. Figure 14 shows the relation between SWAT runoff, SCS curve method runoff, and coupled SWAT-MODFLOW model for different sub-basins of Sunsari district. Similarly, figure 15 presents the same but for Dharan. They highlight the relation between the SWAT output and Coupled SWAT-MODFLOW model. The SWAT and Coupled SWAT-MODFLOW model results are almost identical at each sab-basin, while the output from the SCS curve methods was different at sub-basin no. 56. The total number of Sub-basins divided in Dharan is 102. The result of Surface discharge using SWAT and Coupled SWAT_MODFLOW model is compared. The result in each case is in the same pattern.

Recharge Component in Sunsari District

The recharge pattern and the recharge variation are shown in Figure 16, which varies from 100 to 370 mm/year. To get more detail about the recharge pattern, we dissect four sections at different portions of the study area, as shown in Figure 16. In section I-I, it is cut from South to North at the Western side of the study area where much of the water bodies are found where the recharge values range from 250 mm to 370 mm, which initially gradually increasing and then decreasing progressively from south to north as seen from the graph in Figure 16. Similarly, section II-II, which is also cut South to North as section I-I but selected at the Eastern part of the study area where very few water bodies were located. Recharge value varied from 370 mm to 150 mm from south to north, which initially decreased from 370 mm to 150 mm and then started increasing from 150 mm to 250 mm from the middle of the section, as shown in Figure 20. Two more sections are selected, in which section III-III is in the inner terai area, whereas section IV-IV is in a hilly area from west to east. It is found that the recharge pattern is almost the same in both the cases, but it started decreasing at section III-III from 320 mm to 240 mm, while at section II-II, it is falling again but from 300 mm to 210

mm. From both section III-III and section IV-IV, we found the recharge at the hilly area is less than recharge in the Terai area of Sunsari district.

Figure 16. Recharge pattern at the different cross-sections of Sunsari district

Figure 17. Recharge Pattern in Dharan
Recharge in Dharan City

The recharge pattern and the variation of the recharge are shown in Figure 17. The average recharge of Dharan is found 145mm, and its ranges from 129 mm to 210 mm each year. In Figure 21, the spatial distribution of recharge pattern where we observed that the recharge at each section has a variable value. From that distribution, we got that the recharge near stream and water body is high where at a high hill and slopy area it had low value. For more details of the distribution from south to north and west to east, we dissect sections I-I and section II-II, as shown in Figure 21. When we cut section I-I from south to north, we found recharge values varied from 130 mm to 210 mm, gradually decreasing from south to north, as shown in Figure 17, while it is not gradual at the riverside of the area. Similarly, in section II-II, which is set from west to east, we observe

that recharge variation ranges from 135 mm to 160 mm. Simultaneously, it varies from 135 mm to 210 mm at the riverside, as shown in Figure 17, inferring that the recharge from the river is also significant in value.

Groundwater Component using Coupled SWAT-MODFLOW model

For the model calibration and validation, 27 wells were used as observation wells in the study area in which the 20 wells are shallow, and seven wells are deep tube well. The model's outputs are transmissivity, storage coefficient, and distributed hydraulic conductivity. Using the model, we estimated the drawdown of the well. The value of average transmissivity of Sunsari district is found 1220 m²/day for shallow wells. The transmissivity value for the deep well is observed to be 1860 m²/day, which is almost the same as the recorded value of 1960 m²/day. The specific storage is found in the recorded range, i.e., from 0.0005 to 0.7. We find that the study area's drawdown varies in the range of 1.3 m to 2.4 m. Some of the Bhabar zone regions are also seen having a rising trend in the monsoon season. The value of the rise of the water table is also found very high as 4 m. Water discharge from the HRU is calculated by converting each DHRU. Again, DRU was converted into HRU. After that, the discharge in each sub-basin is computed by calculating the percentage of HRU present in the different portions of the study area. Well observation at different locations is simulated, which showed a very good relationship with the observed data. The simulated results pattern is also the same as that of the pattern followed by the observed data. The drawdown at the different well locations is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18. Water table with Draw-down at the different well location

Groundwater Head

The well observation of different locations was simulated, which showed a very good relationship with the observed

data. The simulated results pattern was also the same as that of the pattern followed by the observed data. The drawdown at different well locations is shown in Figure 19 and Figure 20 show the drawdown at Chadbela, Kusaha, and Tarahara, respectively.

Figure 19. Water table Simulated at Chadbela

Figure 20. Water table Simulated at Tarahara

Conclusions and Summary

This study used the distributed hydrological model SWAT, coupled it with MODFLOW, and applied the integrated model in Nepal’s Eastern region’s watershed. We compared the simulated runoff of SWAT with an empirical method using the SCS curve number method. The model was calibrated and validated using long-term observed datasets and found the performances were in an acceptable range. The performance indicator value was 0.90 and 6.5 for R^2 and NRMS, respectively, in the calibration period, where it was 0.90 and 6.5 for R^2 and NRMS, respectively, in the validation period.

This model was then applied to the whole Sunsari district. We found that the surface runoff was 44%, evapotranspiration loss was 4 %, and groundwater recharge was found 52% of the average rainfall of the Sunsari district. Similarly, we observed that the surface runoff was 48%, evapotranspiration loss only 21%, while recharge was only 31% of the average annual rainfall in Dharan.

The sensitivity analysis of groundwater showed that Hydraulic conductivity variations were more sensible while the storage coefficient was less sensitive to groundwater discharge. Simultaneously, rainfall is more responsible for the recharge, while discharge from the well is more responsible than evapotranspiration.

From this study, we conclude that the southern part of the Sunsari district has plenty of groundwater while in northern part has a scarcity of groundwater storage. So artificial recharge can be applied for the north part of the Sunsari district.

Acknowledgments

We want to thank the Department of Hydrology and Meteorology, Government of Nepal, for sharing hydro meteorological data. We would also like to thank anonymous reviewers for comments and suggestions that greatly enhanced this paper’s quality.

Disclosure Statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Aliyari, Fatemeh, Bailey RT. Environmental Modelling & Software Coupled SWAT-MODFLOW Model for Large-Scale Mixed Agro-Urban River Basins. *Environmental Modelling and Software* 115(February) 2019: 200–210.
2. Ara, Zeenat, Zakwan M. Estimating Runoff Using SCS Curve Number Method. *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering* 2018; 8(5): 195-200.
3. Askar MKh. Rainfall-Runoff Model Using the SCS-CN Method and Geographic Information Systems : A Case Study of Gomal River Watershed. 2014; 178: 159-70.
4. Bailey, Ryan, Rathjens H et al. SWATMOD-Prep: Graphical User Interface for Preparing Coupled SWAT-MODFLOW Simulations. *Journal of the American Water Resources Association* 2017; 53(2): 400-410.
5. Bailey, Ryan T, Wible TC et al. Assessing Regional-Scale Spatio-Temporal Patterns of Groundwater-Surface Water Interactions Using a Coupled SWAT-MODFLOW Model. *Hydrological Processes* 2016; 30(23).
6. Bambara, Apolline, Orban P et al. Quantifying Focused Groundwater Recharge Induced by Irrigation Surface Water Reservoirs in Crystalline Basement Areas for Complementary Irrigation. *Water (Switzerland)* 2020; 12(10): 1-23.
7. Beven, Keith. 2012. Rainfall-Runoff Modelling.
8. Brunner, Philip, Craig T. Simmons, Peter G. Cook, and René Therrien. 2010. Modeling Surface Water-Groundwater Interaction with MODFLOW: Some Considerations. *Ground Water* 48(2):174-80.
9. Chunn, David, Faramarzi M. Application of an Integrated SWAT-MODFLOW Model to Evaluate Potential

- Impacts of Climate Change and Water Withdrawals on Groundwater-Surface Water Interactions in West-Central Alberta. *Water (Switzerland)* 2019; 11(1).
10. Cooley, Richard L. Ground-Water Modeling. *Eos, Transactions American Geophysical Union* 2011; 63(22): 523.
 11. Dong, Yanhui, Guomin Li et al. An Areal Recharge and Discharge Simulating Method for MODFLOW. *Computers and Geosciences* 2012; 42: 203-5.
 12. Dowlatabadi, Sepideh, Zomorodian SMA. Conjunctive Simulation of Surface Water and Groundwater Using SWAT and MODFLOW in Firoozabad Watershed. *KSCCE Journal of Civil Engineering* 2016; 20(1).
 13. Dwarakish GS, Ganasri BP. Impact of Land Use Change on Hydrological Systems: A Review of Current Modeling Approaches. *Cogent Geoscience* 1(1).
 14. Ehtiat, Majid S, Mousavi J et al. Analysis of Recharge Conceptualization in Inverse Groundwater Modelling. *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 2016; 61(15): 2789-2801.
 15. Eshtawi, Tamer, Evers M. Quantifying the Impact of Urban Area Expansion on Groundwater Recharge and Surface Runoff. *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 2016; 61(5): 826-43.
 16. Gao, Fei, Feng G et al. Assessment of Surface Water Resources in the Big Sunflower River Watershed Using Coupled SWAT-MODFLOW Model. *Water (Switzerland)* 2019; 11(3).
 17. Gupta, Dutta S, Mukherjee V et al. Groundwater of South Asia. Springer Singapore 2018.
 18. Hamilton, Pixie. Groundwater and Surface Water: A Single Resource. *Water Environment and Technology* 2005; 17(5): 37-41.
 19. Hashemi, Hossein, Berndtsson R. Artificial Recharge by Floodwater Spreading Estimated by Water Balances and Groundwater Modelling in Arid Iran. *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 60(2): 336-50.
 20. Hughes DA. Incorporating Groundwater Recharge and Discharge Functions into an Existing Monthly Rainfall-Runoff Model. *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 2004; 49(2): 297-312.
 21. Karimi L, Motagh M, Entezam I. Modeling Groundwater Level Fluctuations in Tehran Aquifer: Results from a 3D Unconfined Aquifer Model. *Groundwater for Sustainable Development* 2019; 8: 439-49.
 22. Kim, Won 2019, Chung M et al. The Development of Fully Coupled SWAT-MODFLOW Model (I) Model Development. *Journal of Korea Water Resources Association* 2004; 37(6):499-507.
 23. Kim, Won N, Chung M, Won YS et al. Development and Application of the Integrated SWAT-MODFLOW Model. *Journal of Hydrology* 2008; 356(1&2): 1-16.
 24. Liu, Wei, Park S, Bailey RT et al. Comparing SWAT with SWAT-MODFLOW Hydrological Simulations When Assessing the Impacts of Groundwater Abstractions for Irrigation and Drinking Water 2019: 1-51.
 25. Loucks PD, van Beek E. Water Resource Systems Planning and Analysis - An Introduction to Methods, Models, and Applications 1981; 4.
 26. Loukika KN, Reddy KV, Rao KHVD. Estimation of Groundwater Recharge Rate Using SWAT MODFLOW Model. *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering* 2020; 33.
 27. Melaku, Demelash N, Wang J. A Modified SWAT Module for Estimating Groundwater Table at Lethbridge and Barons, Alberta, Canada. *Journal of Hydrology* 2019; 575: 420-31.
 28. Moghaddam, Kardan H, Moghaddam HK et al. Developing Comparative Mathematic Models, BN and ANN for Forecasting of Groundwater Levels. *Groundwater for Sustainable Development* 2019; 9: 100237.
 29. Mosase, Esther, Ahiablame L et al. Modelling Potential Groundwater Recharge in the Limpopo River Basin with SWAT-MODFLOW. *Groundwater for Sustainable Development* 9, 2019.
 30. Mishra AK. Sustainability and Risk Assessment of Salyankot Water Supply Project in Post-Earthquake Scenario. *International Journal of Operations Management and Information Technology* 2018; 8(1): 1-30. Available at <http://www.ripublication.com>.
 31. Mishra AK, Karna AK. Assessment of Management Transfer Process of Water Supply Systems in Sunsari District of Nepal. *International Journal of Research Granthaalayah* 2019; 7(1): 1-24.
 32. Mishra AK. Institutional Performance Assessment of Water Supply System. *Saudi Journal of Business and Management Studies* 2019; 4(9): 698-707. DOI: 10.36348/sjbms.2019.v04i09.002
 33. Park, Seonggyu, Nielsen A, Bailey RT et al. A QGIS-Based Graphical User Interface for Application and Evaluation of SWAT-MODFLOW Models. *Environmental Modelling and Software* 2019a; 493-97.
 34. Park, Seonggyu, Nielsen A, Bailey RT et al. A QGIS-Based Graphical User Interface for Application and Evaluation of SWAT-MODFLOW Models. *Environmental Modelling and Software* 2019b; 111: 493-97.
 35. Putthividhya, Aksara, Laonamsai J. SWAT and MODFLOW Modeling of Spatio-Temporal Runoff and Groundwater Recharge Distribution. in World Environmental and Water Resources Congress 2017: Groundwater, Sustainability, and Hydro-Climate/Climate Change - Selected Papers from the World Environmental and Water Resources Congress 2017.
 36. Ricka, Adam, Kuchovsky T et al. Identifying the Flow Pattern and Natural Recharge at a Strategic Groundwater Resource in the Dornogobi Province, Mongolia. *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 2018; 63(9): 1408-23.

37. Rossetto, Rudy, Filippis GD et al. Integrating Free and Open Source Tools and Distributed Modelling Codes in GIS Environment for Data-Based Groundwater Management. *Environmental Modelling and Software* 2018; 107.
38. Sherring, Arpan, Rahman TA. Ground Water Mod. 2016; 8.
39. de Silva C, Shanthi, Rushton KR. Groundwater Recharge Estimation Using Improved Soil Moisture Balance Methodology for a Tropical Climate with Distinct Dry Seasons. *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 2007; 52(5): 1051-67.
40. Srinivas A, Rao BV, Rao VVSG. Recharge Process and Aquifer Models of a Small Watershed. *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 1999; 44(5): 681-92.
41. Semiromi, Majid, Manfred Koch. Analysis of Spatio-Temporal Variability of Surface-Groundwater Interactions in the Gharehsoo River Basin, Iran, Using a Coupled SWAT-MODFLOW Model. *Environmental Earth Sciences* 2019; 78(6).
42. Varni, Marcelo, Comas R et al. Application de La Méthode de Fluctuation Du Niveau Piézométrique Pour Caractériser La Recharge Des Eaux Souterraines Dans La Plaine de La Pampa (Argentine). *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 2013; 58(7): 1445-55.
43. Walraevens, Kristine, Vandecasteele I et al. Groundwater Recharge and Flow in a Small Mountain Catchment in Northern Ethiopia. *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 2009; 54(4): 739-53.
44. Wei, Xiaolu and Ryan T. Bailey. Assessment of System Responses in Intensively Irrigated Stream-Aquifer Systems Using SWAT-MODFLOW. *Water (Switzerland)* 2019; 11(8).
45. Xu, Huang G, Zhan H et al. Integration of SWAP and MODFLOW-2000 for Modeling Groundwater Dynamics in Shallow Water Table Areas. *Journal of Hydrology* 2012; 412-413: 170-81.
46. Xu Y, Tonder GJV. Estimation of Recharge Using a Revised CRD Method. *Water SA* 2001; 27(3): 341-43.
47. Zhou, Yangxiao, Wenpeng Li. A Review of Regional Groundwater Flow Modeling. *Geoscience Frontiers* 2011; 2(2): 205-14.
48. Zomorodi K. Evaluation of the Response of a Water Table to a Variable Recharge Rate. *Hydrological Sciences Journal* 1991; 36(1): 67-78.